

Combining AI-powered detection and Immersive Technologies for Robotic Space Mission Planning

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Abstract

Nowadays, space exploration requires automated technologies for the control and navigation of robotic vehicles and spacecrafts: one of the fundamental challenges is to reduce the resource-footprint of the solutions to be put in place, in particular by implementing frugal solutions.

At Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology (LIST), we are focusing on lightweight detection AI-powered methods and algorithms to process high resolution images with few computational resources and low latency. In contrast to the current trend to use increasingly heavy AI models (such as Transformers or Multimodal Large Language Models), we are focusing on the design, training and efficient deployment of tiny AI models [3]. In broad terms, various steps are required for AI models' preparation: reducing as much as possible the number of model parameters before training, then simplifying and compressing the trained models after training, without compromising the accuracy of detection. For the deployment, applying *Resource-aware control* allows to efficiently process continuous streams of images under limited computing, memory and energy consumption conditions [4].

While we are currently employing these techniques in smart telescopes [2] and will be applying them in the coming months to the automatic detection of meteorites from radio data captured in Belgium and Luxembourg ¹, we start to design similar approaches for resource detection on extra-planetary mapping images (Moon, Mars, etc.) using Mixed Reality (MR) hardware. In fact, devices such as Meta Quest 3 or Microsoft HoloLens 2 could be used by to help upstream in the planning of robotic missions tasked with exploring non-terrestrial bodies [1], by using virtual environment enriched by AI embedded models' outputs. For example, visualising and then detecting points of interest, such as possible topographical problems, would help to better organise or even remotely pilot robots or automated vehicles.

¹ <https://www.list.lu/en/informatics/project/need/>

References

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